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Practices of Christian Educators in Handling Children with Special Needs: Basis for Development Training Program for Teachers

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ABSTRACT

Handling children with special needs can present unique challenges for Christian educators, who strive to provide inclusive and supportive environments while integrating faith-based teachings and values. This signifies assessment practices; therefore, the study was designed to investigate Christian educators' competencies, teaching approaches, and the challenges and opportunities encountered in handling children with diverse needs. With this, Robert Katz's three-skill model provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the skills required for effective teachers. Christian educators can unlock their full potential and drive by focusing on developing management skills (technical, human, and conceptual skills). With this, examined the task roles effectively, and their importance varied depending on the level of proficiency and effectiveness in handling children with special needs. The researcher investigates Christian educators' teaching and management skills around Quezon City Philippines Annual Conferences East in the United Methodist Church. The research was a descriptive study using quantitative and qualitative approaches. Data were collected from 36 Pastors and 14 Deaconesses through a survey questionnaire and among them were selected for interview. The collected data were analyzed by descriptive statistics applying mean and std deviation. Primarily, this research has revealed findings regarding the level of competencies of Christian educators, who were proficiently evident in effectively addressing their teaching among students with diverse needs. The study's results illustrated that Christian educators implemented learning through play and music, learning and communication through technology, individualized learning plan, sensory integration techniques, collaboration with parents and professionals, advocacy for inclusion, and equal access of all children in their teaching. Major challenges were sustaining the interest of children, managing challenging behaviors, parental understanding of children's condition, difficulty in navigating religious instruction, lack of awareness and training, and lack of church support for children with special needs. While opportunities for handling children with special needs assessment practices were recognized as; proficiently evident experienced teachers, use of flip teaching approach and development for Christian educators' excellence may be utilized for the professional development of Christian education teachers in teaching practices.

Keywords: Christian Educators; Children with Special Needs; Management Skills; Teaching Approaches; Challenges

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